

Grant Agreement N°763990

UPWARDS

Deliverable D8.1

UPWARDS Website

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¹ Dissemination level: **PU** = Public, **PP** = Restricted to other programme participants (including the JU), **RE** = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the JU), **CO** = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the JU)

² Nature of the deliverable: **R** = Report, **P** = Prototype, **D** = Demonstrator, **O** = Other

³ Creation, modification, final version for evaluation, revised version following evaluation, final

Deliverable abstract

The scope of this deliverable is to present the work, functionalities and concepts behind the UPWARDS website, carried out by Wavestone in collaboration with SINTEF AS.

<https://www.upwards-wind.eu/>

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1. Introduction

A well-made, updated website is one of the most powerful tools for communication and dissemination of key results to broad audiences of all types.

To this end, the UPWARDS website has been conceived to be simple and easily accessible, presenting key messages that may be understood by any kind of stakeholder, from a more specialised audience to the general public.

The main website's contents can be seen in the following figure. Reference to the funding made available by the European Commission and the pertinent disclaimer may be seen at the bottom of the page.

Figure 1 – UPWARDS website homepage

2. Website sections

Apart from the homepage, the website has three main sections, namely:

- **Project’s background**, explained in a few simple paragraphs;
- **UPWARDS’ objectives**, outlining the major goals and why they are critical
- **Project partners’ description**: short description of each partner, with links to each organisation’s website (accessible by clicking in the logos).

Figure 2 – Main sections of the website (please refer to <https://www.upwards-wind.eu/> for a full version of the text)

Furthermore, the website contains two sections that Wavestone will keep updated on a normal basis i.e. monthly, namely:

- **News**: all news related to the project, comprising press releases, assistance to events, as well as Ph. D. and job offers will be published here. All entries will be properly illustrated with pictures, always putting forward the acknowledgement to the funds provided by the European Commission;
- **Publications**: this section will contain both scientific/technical publications and public deliverables. As can be seen in the following figure, these documents will be available for preview and download.

Figure 3 – Publications’ section

Last but not least, there is a contact section with the contact information of the relevant people.

3. Accessibility

Wavestone has made sure that the project website is accessible from different devices and browsers.

IOS

Android

Internet Explorer

4. Updates

The UPWARDS website will undergo continued evolution. The website will be updated with content regularly and promoted across various communication platforms. Specifically, links to the project's Twitter and Facebook accounts are expected to be introduced in the website's homepage in future updates.

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